

Convergence of Monte Carlo Zeta Eigenvalue Simulations

Esmee J. Woods ^{1,*}, Valeria Raffuzzi¹

¹Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, Trumpington Street, Cambridge, CB2 1PZ, United Kingdom

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803495

ABSTRACT

The most common eigenvalue formulation of the neutron transport equation is the k -eigenvalue formulation which ensures criticality by scaling the fission source. Here, our focus is on an alternative scheme, the ζ -eigenvalue formulation, which instead modifies the density of a specific material or nuclide. We investigate the convergence and implementation challenges of the ζ -eigenvalue formulation in Monte Carlo. These ζ -eigenvalue calculations have previously been implemented in Monte Carlo using a fixed-point iteration scheme rather than standard power iteration due to challenges caused by negative operators. However, for fuel-moderator systems the fixed-point iteration scheme has always been observed to converge to the over-moderated solution. Here, we use a simplified two-energy group calculation for a homogenous system to derive an analytical recurrence relation for ζ . This update step shows that the under-moderated solution is always unstable. Additionally, ζ is not guaranteed to converge to the over-moderated solution monotonically, and may become negative. Secondly, using negative weights and weight cancellation, we implement a 1D two-energy group power iteration Monte Carlo formulation of the ζ -eigenvalue equation that modifies the fuel density. As power iteration converges to the largest eigenvalue, this scheme once again produces the over-moderated solution.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, Zeta-Eigenvalue, Stability Analysis, Convergence Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

There exist various formulations of the steady-state neutron transport equation, including the common k -eigenvalue equation which scales the fission source to achieve criticality. Recently, formulations with more practical eigenvalues have been developed, such as a scheme which determines the critical boron concentration in Pressurised Water Reactors [1]. Here we focus on the ζ -eigenvalue formulation, which scales the density of a specified material or nuclide to achieve criticality [2]. This enables the computation of a critical density without relying on expensive repeated eigenvalue simulations which may have their own convergence challenges [3].

Whilst the power iteration formulation of the ζ -eigenvalue equation has been successfully implemented in a deterministic code, a generic fixed-point iteration scheme was used in the Monte Carlo code SCONE due to challenges with implementing negative operators [2, 4, 5]. Negative operators appear as the neutron source for each generation contains a negative collision operator. However, for fuel-moderator systems with two physical critical ζ -eigenvalues, this fixed-point scheme has only been observed to converge to the over-moderated solution.

In this paper, we first discuss the theory of the ζ -eigenvalue formulation, before introducing our two-energy homogeneous problem. In Section 3, we analyse analytically the convergence behaviour of the ζ -eigenvalue and show that the under-moderated solution is always unstable. Finally, in Section 4 we demonstrate a proof of concept 1D implementation of the power iteration formulation in Monte Carlo.

*ejw89@cam.ac.uk

2. THE ζ -EIGENVALUE EQUATION

First, we present a general short-hand notation for the neutron transport equation,

$$\frac{1}{v} \frac{d\psi}{dt} + (L + T - S)\psi = F\psi, \quad (1)$$

where v is the neutron speed, ψ is the angular neutron flux and t is time. The operators L, T, S and F are the streaming, total collision, scattering and fission operators respectively. We split our operators into two parts $O = O_m + O_{\bar{m}}$, where O_m acts on a specified material or nuclide m , and $O_{\bar{m}}$ acts on all other materials. This enables us to scale the density of a material m by ζ , by defining the modified operator $O^\zeta = O_m/\zeta + O_{\bar{m}}$. The steady-state k -eigenvalue equation with a fixed density scaling factor ζ applied to material m is,

$$(L + T^\zeta - S^\zeta)\psi = \frac{F^\zeta\psi}{k}. \quad (2)$$

The ζ -eigenvalue equation solves Equation (2) for a target $k = k_{\text{eff}}^T$ by varying ζ . The following fixed-point iterative scheme has been implemented in Monte Carlo in SCONE [4, 5],

$$(L + T^{\zeta^{(n)}} - S^{\zeta^{(n)}})\psi^{(n+1)} = \frac{F^{\zeta^{(n)}}\psi^{(n)}}{k_\zeta^{(n)}k_{\text{eff}}^T}, \quad (3)$$

where $\psi^{(n)}$ is the neutron flux on iteration n and ζ is updated using,

$$\zeta^{(n)} = \frac{\int_m \left(\frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}^T} F_m + S_m - T_m\right) \psi^{(n)} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{\Omega} dE}{\int_{m+\bar{m}} L\psi^{(n)} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{\Omega} dE - \int_{\bar{m}} \left(\frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}^T} F_{\bar{m}} + S_{\bar{m}} - T_{\bar{m}}\right) \psi^{(n)} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{\Omega} dE}, \quad (4)$$

where the integrals are performed over phase space, where \mathbf{r} is the position, $\mathbf{\Omega}$ the unit angle vector and E the neutron energy. To keep the magnitude of the source term constant, and therefore the total simulated weight in Monte Carlo constant, we have introduced the normalisation factor $k_\zeta^{(n)}$,

$$k_\zeta^{(n)} = k_\zeta^{(0)} \frac{\int F^{\zeta^{(n)}}\psi^{(n)} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{\Omega} dE}{\int F^{\zeta^{(0)}}\psi^{(0)} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{\Omega} dE}, \quad (5)$$

which is equal to 1 when steady-state is reached. As the ζ update step does not depend on $k_\zeta^{(n)}$, the introduction of this factor does not affect convergence of ζ , nor the eigenmodes of the problem. Throughout the rest of this work shall we shall set $k_{\text{eff}}^T = 1$.

Unlike the k -eigenvalue problem, there can be more than one physical ζ -eigenvalue solution. In a fuel-moderator system, there can exist both an under- and over-moderated critical point corresponding to two distinct ζ -eigenvalues. However, the implementation of this fixed-point scheme has been observed to only converge to the over-moderated solution [4]. Here, we develop our understanding of why this occurs by analytically investigating a simplified system.

2.1. Two-Energy Group Model

To understand the stability and convergence behaviour of the fixed-point iteration scheme we define a simple two-energy group model that has two physical ζ solutions. We model neutrons in a periodic

homogeneous medium consisting of two materials, one which is fissile and one which is a moderator. The two-energy group equations are,

$$\begin{cases} \mu \frac{\partial \psi_1^{(n+1)}(x, \mu)}{\partial x} + \Sigma_{t,1}^{\zeta^{(n)}} \psi_1^{(n+1)}(x, \mu) - \frac{1}{2} \Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 1}^{\zeta^{(n)}} \phi_1^{(n+1)} = \frac{1}{2k_{\zeta}^{(n)}} \bar{\nu}_2 \Sigma_{f,2}^{\zeta^{(n)}} \phi_2^{(n)}, \\ \mu \frac{\partial \psi_2^{(n+1)}(x, \mu)}{\partial x} + \Sigma_{t,2}^{\zeta^{(n)}} \psi_2^{(n+1)}(x, \mu) - \frac{1}{2} \Sigma_{s,2 \rightarrow 2}^{\zeta^{(n)}} \phi_2^{(n+1)} - \frac{1}{2} \Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2}^{\zeta^{(n)}} \phi_1^{(n+1)} = 0, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where $\mu = \cos \theta$ gives the scattering angle, subscripts 1 and 2 denote fast and thermal energies, $\bar{\nu}$ is the expected number of fission offspring and Σ_t, Σ_f and $\Sigma_{s,i \rightarrow j}$ are the total, fission, and scattering from energy group $i \rightarrow j$ cross sections respectively. The scalar flux is denoted by ϕ . We have neglected fast fission $\Sigma_{f,1} = 0$, and scattering from thermal to fast energies $\Sigma_{s,2 \rightarrow 1} = 0$. Additionally, we neglect the non-linearity of the multi-group cross sections which in general depend on the neutron flux, and we define $\Sigma^{\zeta} = \Sigma_m / \zeta + \Sigma_{\bar{m}}$. We also make the approximation that no fast neutrons are captured by the moderator, $\Sigma_{\text{mod},c,1} = 0$. The list of cross sections used can be found in Table I.

Table I. Cross Sections used for the two-energy group ζ -eigenvalue calculations.

Material	$\Sigma_{c,1}$	$\Sigma_{c,2}$	$\Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 1}$	$\Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2}$	$\Sigma_{s,2 \rightarrow 2}$	$\Sigma_{f,2}$	$\bar{\nu}_2$
Fuel	0.02	0.1	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.3	2.5
Moderator	0.0	0.02	0.3	0.04	1.0	0.0	-

In steady-state the scalar flux is uniform across the system,

$$\phi_{2,0} = \frac{\Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2}^{\zeta}}{\Sigma_{a,2}^{\zeta}} \phi_{1,0}, \quad \tilde{\Sigma}_{a,1}^{\zeta} \Sigma_{a,2}^{\zeta} = \bar{\nu}_2 \Sigma_{f,2}^{\zeta} \Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2}^{\zeta}, \quad (7)$$

where we define the absorption and effective absorption cross sections as $\Sigma_{a,X} = \Sigma_{t,X} - \Sigma_{s,X}$ and $\tilde{\Sigma}_{a,X} = \Sigma_{t,X} - \Sigma_{s,X \rightarrow X}$ respectively, where $\Sigma_{s,X}$ is the total scattering cross-section for energy group X . As only the moderator scatters neutrons from fast to thermal energies, $\Sigma_{a,2} = \tilde{\Sigma}_{a,2}$ and $\Sigma_{\text{fuel},a,1} = \tilde{\Sigma}_{\text{fuel},a,1}$. The two-energy group solution to Equation (2) for $k = 1$ gives a quadratic in ζ ,

$$\zeta^2 \left(\tilde{\Sigma}_{a,\bar{m},1} \Sigma_{a,\bar{m},2} \right) + \zeta \left(\tilde{\Sigma}_{a,\bar{m},1} \Sigma_{a,m,2} + \tilde{\Sigma}_{a,m,1} \Sigma_{a,\bar{m},2} - \bar{\nu}_2 \Sigma_{f,2} \Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2} \right) + \left(\tilde{\Sigma}_{a,m,1} \Sigma_{a,m,2} \right) = 0, \quad (8)$$

which can give two physical solutions,

$$\zeta_{\pm} = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}, \quad (9)$$

where we define $a = \tilde{\Sigma}_{a,\bar{m},1} \Sigma_{a,\bar{m},2}$, $b = \tilde{\Sigma}_{a,\bar{m},1} \Sigma_{a,m,2} + \tilde{\Sigma}_{a,m,1} \Sigma_{a,\bar{m},2} - \bar{\nu}_2 \Sigma_{f,2} \Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2}$ and $c = \tilde{\Sigma}_{a,m,1} \Sigma_{a,m,2}$. As $a > 0$, $\zeta_+ > \zeta_-$. The dependence of the k -eigenvalue on ζ for m as the moderator is shown in Figure 1.

3. CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS FOR THE FIXED-POINT ITERATION SCHEME

As we are working with periodic boundary conditions, it is useful to decompose the neutron flux into its constituent Fourier modes, i.e. $\phi_1^{(n)} = \sum_m \phi_{1,m}^{(n)} e^{im\pi x/L}$, for a system of length $2L$. As the ζ update-step integrates the flux over the entire system only the $m = 0$ mode from each energy contribute to ζ . We shall use this result to write a compact update step for ζ .

Figure 1. Dependence of the k -eigenvalue on the moderator density scaling factor ζ_{mod} , for the cross-sections given in Table I. There are two solutions to $k = 1$, which correspond to an over-moderated and an under-moderated system.

3.1. Modifying the Moderator Density

First, we consider the case where m is the moderator. The ζ update-step given in Equation (4) becomes,

$$\zeta^{(n)} = \frac{(\Sigma_{s,m,1 \rightarrow 2} - \tilde{\Sigma}_{a,m,1})\phi_{1,0}^{(n)} - \Sigma_{a,m,2}\phi_{2,0}^{(n)}}{\Sigma_{a,\bar{m},1}\phi_{1,0}^{(n)} + (\Sigma_{a,\bar{m},2} - \bar{v}_2\Sigma_{f,\bar{m},2})\phi_{2,0}^{(n)}}. \quad (10)$$

Using Equation (6) we substitute $\phi_{2,0}^{(n)} = \Sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2}^{\zeta^{(n-1)}}\phi_{1,0}^{(n)} / \Sigma_{a,2}^{\zeta^{(n-1)}}$ into Equation (10) to give,

$$\zeta^{(n)} = \frac{-c}{b + a\zeta^{(n-1)}}. \quad (11)$$

To determine the stability of the two roots we define $\Delta_{\pm}^{(n)}$ as the error in ζ on iteration n , $\zeta^{(n)} = \zeta_{\pm} + \Delta_{\pm}^{(n)}$. The update relation for Δ_{\pm} is,

$$\Delta_{\pm}^{(n)} = \frac{\zeta_{\pm}\Delta_{\pm}^{(n-1)}}{\zeta_{\mp} - \Delta_{\pm}^{(n-1)}}. \quad (12)$$

For small $\Delta_{\pm}^{(n-1)}$, $\Delta_{\pm}^{(n)} \approx \frac{\zeta_{\pm}}{\zeta_{\mp}}\Delta_{\pm}^{(n-1)}$. As $\zeta_+ > \zeta_-$, the under-moderated solution ζ_+ is unstable as $|\Delta_+^{(n)}| > |\Delta_+^{(n-1)}|$. No matter the initial guess $\zeta^{(0)}$, convergence will always be to ζ_- . However, ζ is not guaranteed to monotonically converge. The convergence behaviour can be split into three regions,

1. $\zeta^{(n-1)} < \zeta_+ \rightarrow |\Delta_-^{(n)}| < |\Delta_-^{(n-1)}|$ and ζ converges to ζ_- monotonically.
2. $\zeta_+ < \zeta^{(n-1)} < \zeta_+ + \zeta_- \rightarrow 0 < \Delta_-^{(n-1)} < \Delta_-^{(n)}$. ζ initially moves away from ζ_- , until criteria 3 is reached.
3. $\zeta_+ + \zeta_- < \zeta^{(n-1)} \rightarrow \zeta^{(n)} < 0$ and ζ subsequently converges to ζ_- as criteria 1 is now met.

The analytical convergence behaviour discussed above is in good agreement with results from single runs of two-energy group Monte Carlo simulations using 1,000,000 particles for different $\zeta^{(0)}$ values, as

shown in Figure 2. When $\zeta^{(n)}$ becomes negative, we terminate the Monte Carlo simulation as it cannot currently treat $\zeta^{(n)} < 0$. We also show the convergence of the normalisation factor,

$$k_{\zeta}^{(n)} = \frac{\bar{v}_2 \sum_{f,2}^{\zeta^{(n)}} \sum_{s,1 \rightarrow 2}^{\zeta^{(n-1)}}}{\sum_{a,2}^{\zeta^{(n-1)}} \sum_{a,1}^{\zeta^{(n-1)}}}, \quad (13)$$

which tends to 1. We note that $k_{\zeta}^{(n)}$ is only equivalent to the k -eigenvalue for $\zeta^{(n)}$ once steady-state is reached.

Figure 2. Convergence of the ζ -eigenvalue to ζ_- and the fission source normalisation factor $k_{\zeta}^{(n)}$ to 1 using the fixed-point iteration scheme, when the moderator is the ζ -material. Different colours correspond to different starting $\zeta^{(0)}$ values, leading to different convergence behaviours. Straight lines are drawn between successive points to guide the eye. The under-moderated solution ζ_+ is unstable.

3.2. Modifying the Fuel Density

We now follow a similar process for m as the fuel. The update relations for ζ and its error become,

$$\zeta^{(n)} = \frac{-b\zeta^{(n-1)} - c}{a\zeta^{(n-1)}}, \quad \Delta_{\pm}^{(n)} = \frac{\zeta_{\mp} \Delta_{\pm}^{(n-1)}}{\zeta_{\pm} + \Delta_{\pm}^{(n-1)}}. \quad (14)$$

The ζ_- solution is now unstable, which once again corresponds to the under-moderated solution. As before, we can examine the convergence behaviour by considering three regions,

1. $\zeta_- < \zeta^{(n-1)} \rightarrow |\Delta_+^{(n)}| < |\Delta_+^{(n-1)}|$ and ζ converges to ζ_+ monotonically.
2. $0 < \zeta^{(n-1)} < \zeta_- \rightarrow \Delta_-^{(n)} < \Delta_-^{(n-1)} < 0$. ζ initially moves away from ζ_+ , until criteria 3 is reached.
3. $\zeta^{(n-1)} < 0 \rightarrow \zeta_+ + \zeta_- < \zeta^{(n)}$ and ζ subsequently converges to ζ_+ as criteria 1 is met.

These analytic update relations are in good agreement with the observed convergence behaviour in Figure 3.

We have shown that fixed-point ζ -eigenvalue simulations using two-energy groups to model a homogenous fuel-moderator medium will always converge ζ to the over-moderated solution. Therefore, the under-moderated solution is unstable even without considering the non-linearity of cross-sections.

Figure 3. Convergence of the ζ -eigenvalue to ζ_+ and the fission source normalisation factor $k_{\zeta}^{(n)}$ to 1 using the fixed-point iteration scheme, when the fuel is the ζ -material. Different colours correspond to different starting $\zeta^{(0)}$ values. Straight lines are drawn between successive points to guide the eye. The under-moderated solution ζ_- is unstable.

4. MONTE CARLO ζ -EIGENVALUE POWER ITERATION

Power iteration simulations of the ζ -eigenvalue formulation solve,

$$(L + T_{\bar{m}} - S_{\bar{m}} - F_{\bar{m}})\psi^{(n+1)} = \frac{1}{\zeta^{(n)}}(F_m + S_m - T_m)\psi^{(n)}. \quad (15)$$

This scheme has been successively implemented in deterministic codes to compute ζ [2, 4]. As power iteration converges to the largest eigenvalue, it is possible to converge to the under- or over-moderated solution by setting m as the moderator or fuel respectively. However, representing negative operators in Monte Carlo is more challenging.

4.1. Monte Carlo Implementation

The operators on the left hand side of Equation (15) act on $\psi^{(n+1)}$ and therefore affect particles tracked in the current generation, whilst the operators on the right hand side populate the particle bank for the next generation, which we shall refer to as the source bank. Therefore, negative operators on the left hand side produce particles in the current generation, whilst negative operators on the right hand side remove particles from the source bank.

When a particle collides with m , instead of removing the particle from the current generation we should remove a particle at the corresponding position in phase space from the source bank. However, we cannot remove a particle from the source bank that does not yet exist. Instead, we duplicate the incoming particle of weight w , to produce a new particle at the same position in phase space, but with weight $-w$. This particle is added to the source bank. Then we sample the interaction type, and add scattered or fission neutrons to the source bank as appropriate. The weight of these neutrons has the same sign as w . As the incoming particle has not been removed from the current generation, the distance to its next

collision point is sampled and the process is repeated. As an example in Figure 4, we consider the case where a neutron of weight w interacts with material m and is scattered.

Figure 4. Negative weight example for a neutron of weight w scattering from material m .

This means particles are only removed from the current generation when they are captured by \bar{m} . When \bar{m} produces more neutrons through fission than it captures, the total weight of particles tracked through the current generation will increase. Therefore, we only consider the scenario where \bar{m} is the moderator.

The source bank for generations $n > 1$ will contain particles with a mixture of positive and negative weights. Whilst the sum of the particle weights W_{tot} is kept constant through normalisation by the ζ -eigenvalue, the sum of the absolute weights W_{abs} will grow. To keep W_{abs} and the total number of particles simulated low enough, weight cancellation techniques must be used [6, 7]. However, as T_m only produces particles at the same point in phase space as the incoming particle, these weight cancellation techniques do not extend well to 3D.

We test the above Monte Carlo implementation for a 1D rod model with left and right transport, for m as the fuel. As expected from power iteration, the ζ -eigenvalue converges to the larger of the two solutions ζ_+ , which still corresponds to the over-moderated solution. The estimates of the ζ -eigenvalue from Monte Carlo simulations starting with an initial source bank of 100,000 particles with different thermal to fast energy ratios are shown in Figure 5. Whilst convergence is rapid for all tested initial conditions the stochastic noise is large.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work has analysed the convergence behaviour of the fixed-point iteration formulation of the ζ -eigenvalue equation, which scales the density of a specified material to achieve criticality. In a fuel-moderator system two physical solutions to ζ can exist. However, previous work has only observed convergence to the over-moderated solution no matter the starting value $\zeta^{(0)}$, or which material density is scaled by ζ . By modelling a homogeneous mixture of fuel and moderator with two energy groups, we derive an analytic update relation for ζ . This recurrence relation shows that the under-moderated solution is always unstable. Whilst mathematically the ζ -eigenvalue will always converge to the over-moderated solution, it may not do so monotonically and can briefly become negative. Future work in this area will involve investigating the applicability of stabilisation techniques used in non-linear analysis for guiding the fixed-point iteration scheme to the under-moderated solution.

Secondly, as a proof of concept, we implement the power iteration formulation of the ζ -eigenvalue equation in Monte Carlo in 1D rod geometry, by representing the removal of particles by the creation of particles with negative weight, and utilising weight cancellation techniques. However, the stochastic noise is high and this technique does not appear to be extendable to 3D systems.

Figure 5. Estimates of the ζ -eigenvalue for power iteration Monte Carlo simulations, in which m is the fuel. The error bars show the standard deviation over five independent runs. The different colours correspond to different starting ratios of fast to thermal energies $\phi_{1,0}^{(0)} : \phi_{2,0}^{(0)}$. Whilst convergence rapidly occurs to the over-moderated solution ζ_+ , the stochastic noise is large.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the EPSRC grant MaThRad (EP/W026899/1). We thank Nicolò Abrate for useful discussions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Jo and N. Cho. “Inline critical boron concentration search with p-CMFD feedback in whole-core continuous-energy Monte Carlo simulation.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 120**, pp. 402–409 (2018). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2018.05.050>.
- [2] N. Abrate, S. Dulla, P. Ravetto, and P. Saracco. “A generalized eigenvalue formulation for core-design applications.” *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 197**(8), pp. 2047–2071 (2023). URL <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295639.2022.2134685>.
- [3] D. Mancusi and A. Zoia. “Chaos in eigenvalue search methods.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 112**, pp. 354–363 (2018). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2017.10.022>.
- [4] V. Raffuzzi, N. Abrate, and S. Dulla. “Monte Carlo and Deterministic Implementations of the Zeta-Eigenvalue Equation for Efficient Criticality Searches.” *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, pp. 1–15 (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295639.2025.2568341>.
- [5] V. Raffuzzi, P. Cosgrove, and M. Kowalski. “Status of the SCONE Monte Carlo neutron transport code.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 227**, p. 112015 (2026).
- [6] T. Booth and J. Gubernatis. “Exact regional Monte Carlo weight cancellation for second eigenfunction calculations.” *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 165**(3), pp. 283–291 (2010). URL <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE09-62>.
- [7] H. Belanger, D. Mancusi, and A. Zoia. “Exact weight cancellation in Monte Carlo eigenvalue transport problems.” *Physical Review E*, **volume 104**(1), p. 015306 (2021). URL <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.104.015306>.